

A HEALTHY DIET THROUGH THE LIFE-COURSE: THE LAST WHO RECOMMENDATIONS

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Introduction

A healthy lifestyle aims to strengthen human health, as well as to prevent diseases. To achieve these goals, a person needs to be physically active, eat healthy food, follow hygiene rules, give up bad habits, and follow tips aimed at strengthening the body and human health. The healthy diet becomes, however, one of the most important components of a healthy lifestyle.

Material and methods

The last WHO/FAO guidelines and recommendations concerning healthy diet were reviewed to select best evidence-based approach for healthy life. Only statements based on prospective studies (RCTs, cohort-studies) and their systematic reviews and meta-analyses were considered as the source for the final recommendations.

Results

WHO has updated its three (3) guidance on total fat, saturated and trans-fat and carbohydrates, based on the latest scientific evidence, by 2023. Totally, we reviewed nine guidelines concerning rations on diets for adults (≥ 18 y.o.) and children of different ages. A healthy diet **for adults** includes the following: a) at least 400 g (i.e. five portions) of fruit and vegetables per day, excluding potatoes, sweet potatoes and other starchy roots, and 25 g of dietary fibre per day; b) total fat intake to 30% of total energy intake or less, saturated fatty acid intake to 10% of total energy intake and no more than 1% of total energy intake coming from trans-fatty acids; c) less than 5 g of iodized salt (one teaspoon). A healthy diet **for children** includes the following: a) 2–5 years old, at least 250 g per day, 6–9 years old, at least 350 g per day, 10 years or older, at least 400 g per day of fruits and vegetables; 2–5 years old, at least 15 g per day, 6–9 years old, at least 21 g per day, 10 years or older, at least 25 g per day of fibre; c) fats rations on diet of children are the same as in the adults; d) infants should be breastfed exclusively during the first 6 months of life, infants should be breastfed continuously until 2 years of age and beyond, from 6 months of age, breast milk should be complemented with a variety of adequate, safe and nutrient-dense foods; e) salt and sugars should not be added to complementary foods.

Discussion

The provided recommendations are ones that are based on only the strongest evidence from the prospective studies and their systematic reviews. However, less strong recommendations can be applied to formulate such recommendations on rations that are not provided previously, with stressing all possible limitations on evidence.

Conclusions

These new guidelines, together with existing WHO guidelines on free sugars, non-sugar sweeteners and sodium, as well as forthcoming guidelines on polyunsaturated fatty acids and low-sodium salt substitutes, underpin the concept of healthy diets.

References:

1. Total fat intake for the prevention of unhealthy weight gain in adults and children: WHO guideline. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.
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